

ACTA GEOGRAPHICA SLOVENICA

GEOGRAFSKI
ZBORNIK

2021
61
2

ACTA GEOGRAPHICA SLOVENICA

GEOGRAFSKI ZBORNIK

61-2 • 2021

Contents

Dordije VASILJEVIĆ, Milica BEGAN, Miroslav VUJIČIĆ, Thomas HOSE, Uglješa STANKOV <i>Does geosite interpretation lead to conservation? A case study of the Sićevo Gorge (Serbia)</i>	7
Gabrijela POPOVIĆ, Dragiša STANUJKIĆ, Predrag MIMOVIĆ, Goran MILOVANOVIĆ, Darjan KARABAŠEVIĆ, Pavle BRZAKOVIĆ, Aleksandar BRZAKOVIĆ <i>An integrated SWOT – extended PIPRECIA model for identifying key determinants of tourism development: The case of Serbia</i>	23
Robert KALBARCZYK, Eliza KALBARCZYK <i>Precipitation variability, trends and regions in Poland: Temporal and spatial distribution in the years 1951–2018</i>	41
Ivana CRLJENKO, Matjaž GERŠIČ <i>A comparison of the beginnings of exonym standardization in Croatian and Slovenian</i>	73
Tadej BREZINA, Jernej TIRAN, Matej OGRIN, Barbara LAA <i>COVID-19 impact on daily mobility in Slovenia</i>	91
Maruša GOLUŽA, Maruška ŠUBIC-KOVAČ, Drago KOS, David BOLE <i>How the state legitimizes national development projects: The Third Development Axis case study, Slovenia</i>	109
Tin LUKIĆ, Tanja MICIĆ PONJIGER, Biljana BASARIN, Dušan SAKULSKI, Milivoj GAVRILOV, Slobodan MARKOVIĆ, Matija ZORN, Blaž KOMAC, Miško MILANOVIĆ, Dragoslav PAVIĆ, Minučer MESAROŠ, Nemanja MARKOVIĆ, Uroš DURLEVIĆ, Cezar MORAR, Aleksandar PETROVIĆ <i>Application of Angot precipitation index in the assessment of rainfall erosivity: Vojvodina Region case study (North Serbia)</i>	123
Janij OBLAK, Mira KOBOLD, Mojca ŠRAJ <i>The influence of climate change on discharge fluctuations in Slovenian rivers</i>	155
Vladimir STOJANOVIĆ, Dubravka MILIĆ, Sanja OBRADOVIĆ, Jovana VANOVAČ, Dimitrije RADIŠIĆ <i>The role of ecotourism in community development: The case of the Zasavica Special Nature Reserve, Serbia</i>	171
Marko V. MILOŠEVIĆ, Dragoljub ŠTRBAC, Jelena ČALIĆ, Milan RADOVANOVIĆ <i>Detection of earthflow dynamics using medium-resolution digital terrain models: Diachronic perspective of the Jovac earthflow, Southern Serbia</i>	187

ISSN 1581-6613

APPLICATION OF ANGOT PRECIPITATION INDEX IN THE ASSESSMENT OF RAINFALL EROSIVITY: VOJVODINA REGION CASE STUDY (NORTH SERBIA)

Tin Lukić, Tanja Micić Ponjiger, Biljana Basarin, Dušan Sakulski, Milivoj Gavrilov, Slobodan Marković, Matija Zorn, Blaž Komac, Miško Milanović, Dragoslav Pavić, Minučer Mesaroš, Nemanja Marković, Uroš Durlević, Cezar Morar, Aleksandar Petrović

Rainfall erosivity in Vojvodina (North Serbia).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS.8754>

UDC: 911.2:556.12:504.121(497.113)

COBISS: 1.01

Tin Lukić¹, Tanja Micić Ponjiger¹, Biljana Basarin¹, Dušan Sakulski², Milivoj Gavrilov¹, Slobodan Marković¹, Matija Zorn³, Blaž Komac³, Miško Milanović⁴, Dragoslav Pavić¹, Minučer Mesaroš¹, Nemanja Marković¹, Uroš Durlević⁴, Cezar Morar⁵, Aleksandar Petrović⁶

Application of Angot precipitation index in the assessment of rainfall erosivity: Vojvodina Region case study (North Serbia)

ABSTRACT: The paper aims to provide an overview of the most important parameters (the occurrence, frequency and magnitude) in Vojvodina Region (North Serbia). Monthly and annual mean precipitation values in the period 1946–2014, for the 12 selected meteorological stations were used. Relevant parameters (precipitation amounts, Angot precipitation index) were used as indicators of rainfall erosivity. Rainfall erosivity index was calculated and classified throughout precipitation susceptibility classes liable of triggering soil erosion. Precipitation trends were obtained and analysed by three different statistical approaches. Results indicate that various susceptibility classes are identified within the observed period, with a higher presence of very severe rainfall erosion in June and July. This study could have implications for mitigation strategies oriented towards reduction of soil erosion by water.

KEY WORDS: climate change, precipitation, rainfall erosivity, soil erosion, Angot precipitation index, Vojvodina, Serbia.

¹ University of Novi Sad, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management; Novi Sad, Serbia lukic021@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5398-0928>), tanja.micic91@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5549-2693>), biljana.basarin@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2546-3728>), gavrilov.milivoj@gmail.com, baca.markovic@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4977-634X>), dragoslav.pavic@dgt.uns.ac.rs (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7113-0887>), minucher@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2505-5633>), nemanja123markovic@gmail.com

² University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute; Novi Sad, Serbia dsakulski2@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4926-2824>)

³ Research centre of the Slovenian academy of sciences and arts, Anton Melik Geographical Institute; Ljubljana, Slovenia matija.zorn@zrc-sazu.si (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5788-018X>), blaz.komac@zrc-sazu.si (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4205-5790>)

⁴ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography, Department of Geospatial Bases of Environment; Belgrade, Serbia misko@gef.bg.ac.rs (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7245-0700>), durlevicuros@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3497-5239>)

⁵ University of Oradea, Department of Geography, Tourism and Territorial Planning; Oradea, Romania cezarmorar@yahoo.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0211-5883>)

⁶ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography, Department of Physical Geography; Belgrade, Serbia bebek2005@gmail.com (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1172-3875>)

Uporaba padavinski indeksa Angot za oceno erozivnosti padavin: na primeru Vojvodine (severna Srbija)

POVZETEK: Prispevek podaja pregled najpomembnejših padavinskih parametrov (pojavnost, pogostost in velikost) v Vojvodini (severna Srbija). Za 12 izbranih meteoroloških postaj so bile uporabljene mesečne in letne povprečne vrednosti padavin v obdobju 1946–2014. Kot kazalnike erozivnosti padavin smo uporabili ustrezne padavinske parametre (količina padavin, padavinski indeks Angot). Izračunali smo indeks erozivnosti padavin in ga razvrstili v razrede glede na možnost pojavljanja erozije prsti. Trende smo preučili s tremi različnimi statističnimi pristopi. V preučevanem obdobju smo prepoznali različne razrede indeksa, z zelo močno padavin erozijo junija in julija. Raziskava je dober temelj za oblikovanje strategij, usmerjenih v zmanjšanje vodne erozije prsti.

KLJUČNE BESEDE: podnebne spremembe, padavine, erozivnost padavin, erozija prsti, padavinski indeks Angot, Vojvodina, Srbija

The article was submitted for publication on May 31st, 2020.
Uredništvo je prejelo prispevek 31. maja 2020.

1 Introduction

One of the most prominent causes of land degradation is water erosion (Boardman and Poesen 2006; Bosco et al. 2015). »Erosion is a geomorphic process that detaches and removes material (soil, rock debris, and associated organic matter) from its primary location by some natural erosive agents or through human or animal activity« (Zorn and Komac 2013a, 288). Soil erosion is an important process connected to several erosive agents, such as water, wind, ice, and snow (Morgan 2005; Blinkov 2015a; Blinkov 2015b). Panagos et al. (2015a; 2015b) pointed out that in Europe, soil erosion by water accounts for the greatest soil loss compared to other erosion processes (e.g., Boardman and Poesen 2006). Water erosion may be accelerated by human activity, but human activity may also prevent runoffs and soil removal by building retention ponds (Ferk et al. 2020) or terraces (Šmid Hribar et al. 2017).

Water erosion has many on-site and off-site effects (Santos Telles, de Fátima Guimarães and Falci Dechen 2011), whereby off-site effects may have greater social, economic and environmental concern (Boardman et al. 2019). Soil erosion affects land resources and increases the risk posed by the blockage of rivers and causes degradation of water quality through pesticides, fertilizers and nutrients carried with the sediment (Lukić et al. 2019). Although soils represent a vital resource, research on soil erosion has not gained as much attention as degradation of water and air quality (Blinkov 2015a). The reason can be found in much more complex and extensive natural factors that led to this type of erosion, which are almost impossible to explain with a model that would consist of every variable and factor included in the process. Nevertheless, land degradation is recognized as a major environmental threat in many parts of Europe (e.g., de Luis, González-Hidalgo and Longares 2010; de Luis et al. 2011; Blinkov 2015a; Blinkov 2015b; Lukić et al. 2013, 2016, 2018, 2019; Zorn and Komac 2013b).

Soil erosion may be quantified using field measurement (Stroosnijder 2005) or erosion models (Borrelli et al. 2021). Globally the most widely used erosion models belong to *Universal Soil Loss Equation* family (*USLE/RUSLE* (Wischmeier and Smith 1978; Renard et al. 1997)), whereas on the territory of former Yugoslavia and in some neighbouring countries the Gavrilović equation has predominated (Gavrilović 1972; Hrvatinić et al. 2019). Besides these, there are more than 600 other models that can be divided into two basic groups: those extracted from the *USLE* and *RUSLE* equations, while others employ qualitative approaches (Auerswald et al. 2014).

Precipitation is the most important natural agent with regard to water soil erosion, hence representing one of the determining factors in the *USLE* equation (Wischmeier and Smith 1978; Morgan 2005; Mello et al. 2013). The capability of rainfall to cause soil loss is called rainfall erosivity (Nearing et al. 2017; Panagos et al. 2017) and represents a climatological component in the overall erosion processes by water (da Silva 2004; Yu 1998). It is fundamental for the understanding of the climatic vulnerability regarding soil erosion

in a given region (Panagos et al. 2015a). Several measures of rainfall erosivity have been proposed (Yu and Neil 2000; Morgan 2005):

- *R*-factor in the *USLE/RUSLE* (Wischmeier and Smith 1978; Renard et al. 1997),
- Fournier's Index (Fournier 1960),
- Modified Fournier Index (Arnoldus 1980),
- Lal's AI_m index (Lal 1976),
- Hudson's $KE > 1$ Index (Hudson 1976), and
- Onchev's Universal Erosivity Index (Onchev 1985).

Rainfall erosivity presents the potential of raindrops to trigger soil erosion and its estimation is fundamental for the understanding of the climatic vulnerability of a given region (Mello et al. 2013). Thereby, respective authors (e.g., Kirkby and Neale 1987; de Luis, González-Hidalgo and Longares 2010; de Luis et al. 2011) investigated the relationship between the intensity of precipitation and its distribution in time, since there is no exact relationship between the total amount of precipitation and soil erosion. Different approaches have been developed when estimating soil erosion, namely indices based on precipitation data, and indices based on kinetic energy and precipitation intensity (e.g., Lukić et al. 2016; 2019). The most recognized indices describing kinetic energy and precipitation intensity are EI_{30} (Weischmeier and Smith, 1978), AI_m (Lal 1976), $KE > 1$ (Hudson 1976) and P/\sqrt{t} (Onchev 1985). These parameters require daily precipitation data series over 20 years, and since there is no such data for most parts of the world, it was necessary to create a simpler approach. The most utilized indices based on available rainfall data are the Fournier Index (*FI*) and the Modified Fournier Index (*MFI*) (Morgan 2005; Arnoldus 1980) which are extracted from the *R* – rainfall erosivity factor in the *USLE* equation (Renard and Freimund 1994; Gabriels 2001; Loureiro and Coutinho 2001; Diodato and Bellocchi 2007). They were used in numerous studies with scarce precipitation databases (e.g., Lujan and Gabriels 2005; Boardman and Poesen 2006; de Luis, González-Hidalgo and Longares 2010; Ufoegbune et al. 2011; Costea 2012; Lukić et al. 2016; 2018; 2019). It was also in comparisons of several rainfall erosivity indices (e.g., Oduro-Afriyie 1996; da Silva 2004; Bayramin, Erpul and Erdogan 2006; Angulo-Martínez and Beguería 2009; Alipour et al. 2012; Mello et al. 2013; Sanchez-Moreno, Mannaerts and Jetten 2014). Fournier indices require mean monthly data averages and are based on temporal precipitation distribution obtained through Precipitation Concentration Index (*PCI*) (Arnoldus 1980). Beside articles that were based on *MFI* and *FI* parameters (e.g., Oduro-Afriyie 1996; Lujan and Gabriels 2005; Apaydin et al. 2006; Costea 2012; Yue, Shi and Fang 2014; Hernando and Romana 2015), *PCI* was also used in numerous studies concerning precipitation distribution and concentration (Martínez-Casasnovas, Ramos and Ribes-Dasi 2002; de Luis et al. 2011; Iskander, Rajib and Rahman 2014; Lukić et al. 2019).

According to Dumitrascu et al. (2017), besides soil type, topography, and land use, the amount and intensity of precipitation is an important factor in estimating the rate of soil erosion by water. The climatic factors can lead to the intensification of erosion when they register high intensities and occurrence after a prolonged drought period.

For this purpose, an indicator for the assessment of pluvial aggressiveness (Angot – *K* index) (Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008) can be applied in assessing rainfall erosivity in Southeastern Europe – a hotspot region with the highest number of severely affected sectors (Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008; Dragotă et al. 2014; Dumitrascu et al. 2017; Lung and Hilden 2017; Lukić et al. 2019; Milanović et al. 2019). So far, rainfall erosivity assessment in the Vojvodina Region has been carried out in the Bačka and Zemun loess plateaus (Lukić et al. 2016, 2018) and in the Pannonian Basin (Lukić et al. 2019). The study found that the amount and the intensity of precipitation are increasing. According to Marković et al. (2008; 2012; 2015), the largest part of Vojvodina is covered with loess and loess-like sediments (> 60%), which are extremely susceptible to the erosion processes due to high porosity, carbonate and clay content as abounding material (Lukić et al. 2009; Vasiljević et al. 2011; Hrnjak et al. 2014). Therefore, it is very important to point out the most vulnerable areas for mitigation and prevention (Leger 1990; Lukić et al. 2016; 2019).

The publicly available precipitation database of the Vojvodina Region record more than 70 years of continuous observations. However, the data is based on monthly values. Accordingly, the aforementioned Angot – *K* index, which was used in similar studies (in the neighbouring countries), is one of the compatible methodological approaches for assessing the potential vulnerability of the investigated area from the rainfall erosivity (e.g., Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008; Dragotă et al. 2014; Dumitrascu et al. 2017).

So far, rainfall erosivity assessment in the Vojvodina Region has been carried out for the case study of Kula settlement (southern part of the Bačka loess plateau) and Zemun area in the vicinity of Belgrade (Zemun

loess plateau), where Lukić et al. (2016; 2018) studied the relationship between recurring landslides and rainfall erosivity. In a later study, Lukić et al. (2019) showed an increase in the amount and the intensity of precipitation as well as in rainfall erosivity for most parts of the Pannonian Basin, including Vojvodina region.

In this paper climatological parameters from the Vojvodina Region (North Serbia) are processed. We used the Angot precipitation index (Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008), which is the ratio of the daily average volume of precipitation in a month and the annual daily average precipitation volume (Constantin and Vătămanu 2015) and was previously already used in the wider study region by Dragotă et al. (2014) and Dumitrașcu et al. (2017). In order to assess the erosion vulnerability for the southern part of the Pannonian Basin, the occurrence, frequency and magnitude of some of the most significant precipitation parameters were studied.

2 Study area

The Autonomous Province of Vojvodina (21,533 km²) is located in the southern part of the Pannonian Basin and the northern part of the Republic of Serbia (Figure 1). It is divided into three regions: Banat, Bačka, and Srem with Novi Sad as the capital (Basarin et al. 2018; Gavrilov et al. 2020).

The largest part of the region is covered with loess and loess-like sediments (> 60%). As the loess material possesses several properties which make it highly susceptible to water erosion, it is very important to point out the most vulnerable areas for mitigation and prevention (Leger 1990; Lukić et al. 2009; 2016; 2019).

The Vojvodina Region is predominantly a lowland area, and the highest parts are Fruška gora Mountain (539 m) in the northern part of the Srem Region, and the Vršacke Mountains (641 m) in the southeastern part of the Banat Region. However, the largest geomorphological structures are formed on loess and loess-like material, and present loess plateaus, terraces and microrelief forms (Marković et al. 2008; 2012; 2015; Lukić et al. 2009; Vasiljević et al. 2011; Gavrilov et al. 2020).

The climate of the Vojvodina Region is controlled by the geographical position in the southern part of the Pannonian Basin. According to the Köppen climate classification it is moderately continental due to the weaker impact of western air currents, and the greater impact of a Eurasian continental climate. Winter seasons are cold (average January temperatures range from < 0.0 °C to 1.0 °C), while summers are hot and humid (average July temperature of between 21.0 °C and 23.0 °C), with a huge temperature range, reaching ~70 °C and very irregular distribution of monthly rainfall (extremely rainy early summer and low precipitation in November and March) (Malinović-Miličević et al. 2018). Climate is influenced by NW cold and humid wind, and the warm and dry SE wind. Hence, the main characteristic of the rainfall regime in Vojvodina is reflected in the pronounced variability in both space and time. The average annual precipitation is 606 mm, with the highest amounts in June, and lowest in February (Gavrilov et al. 2015; 2016). During the summer the total monthly precipitation can fall within a single day. The lowest average annual rainfall of about 540 mm is recorded in the north, while the highest average precipitation values are recorded in the southwest of Vojvodina (Hrnjak et al. 2014; Tošić et al. 2014; Gavrilov et al. 2019).

3 Data and methods

The precipitation data for the rainfall erosivity assessment was obtained from the database of the Hydro-meteorological Service of the Republic of Serbia for the period 1946–2014 for 12 meteorological stations (Meteorološki godišnjak 1946–2014) (Table 1), selected based on the completeness of the time series and spatial distribution (Figure 1). Data for the analysed period covers two thirty-year cycles, which is in accordance with the WMO standards.

Datasets for each of the stations were analysed and processed for the calculation of the mean monthly amount of precipitation. Thus, a database was created with a time series of monthly and annual precipitation values. The homogeneity of the precipitation series was confirmed by the Alexandersson (1986) test. Precipitation trends were examined using three different statistical approaches. In the first approach, a simple linear regression was used to determine the existence of a certain tendency in the data series, which gives information on the stagnation, growth or decline of the observed phenomenon (Cohen 1988; Gocić and Trajković 2013). Using

Table 1: Geographical coordinates and altitudes of selected meteorological stations.

Region	Meteorological stations	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Altitude (m)
Banat	Banatski Karlovac	45°03'00"	21°02'12"	100
	Bela Crkva	44°54'00"	21°25'12"	90
	Vršac	45°09'00"	21°19'12"	83
	Zrenjanin	45°22'00"	20°25'00"	80
	Kikinda	45°51'00"	20°28'12"	81
	Senta	45°55'48"	20°04'48"	80
Bačka	Bač	44°54'00"	21°25'12"	90
	Bački Petrovac	45°22'12"	19°34'12"	85
	Palić	46°06'00"	19°46'12"	102
	Rimski Šančevi	45°19'48"	19°51'00"	86
	Sombor	45°46'12"	19°09'00"	87
Srem	Sremska Mitrovica	45°01'00"	19°33'00"	82

this method, the trend equation for yearly data was obtained for 69 years. The precipitation trend was also investigated using the nonparametric Mann-Kendall test, which is widely applied in environmental sciences for its simplicity and precision (Gilbert 1987; Gavrilov et al. 2011, 2013; Hrnjak et al. 2014; Lukić et al. 2017). Third, Kendall's tau (τ) (Kendall 1938, 1975) was calculated to gain a trend over a fully observed period of 69 years. Then, two hypotheses were tested:

- 1) Null hypothesis (H_0) – with the assertion that there is no trend in the observed time series for a defined level of significance of 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$);
- 2) Alternative hypothesis (H_a) – with the assertion that there is a trend in a given time series for a defined level of significance of 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Statistical data processing was performed using the Wolfram Mathematica 11.3 software. Due to the presence of a positive correlation in data sets that can influence the increase in the number of false-positive trend outcomes, the Yue-Pilon method was performed (Yue et al. 2002).

Rainfall erosivity can be assessed using several methods (Costea 2012), of which we choose Angot precipitation index (K) (Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008; Dragotă et al. 2014; Dumitraşcu et al. 2017). According to Dumitraşcu et al. (2017), destructive heavy rainfalls mostly depend on the intensity, duration and water quantity of the precipitation, and particular surface features, such as lithology, vegetation cover, and slope. In such conditions, heavy precipitation can trigger floods, erosion and slope failures (Lukić et al. 2016, 2018). Hence, the main components of the precipitation regime that have the strongest impact on the environment in the Vojvodina Region have been analysed using a specific erodibility K index. According to Dumitraşcu et al. (2017), this index has the benefit of relying on easily accessible input data (precipitation), where the quantification and ranking of precipitation aggressiveness is made using already established value classes. The Angot precipitation index (K) was initially aimed at determining the characteristic types of monthly and annual variation of precipitation based on regional and local comparisons. The index was quantified according to equations 1 and 2 (Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008; Dumitraşcu et al. 2017):

$$K = \frac{p}{P} \quad (1)$$

where $p = q/n$, q being the monthly precipitation amounts, and n being the number of days/months, and

$$P = \frac{Q}{365} \quad (2)$$

where Q is the multiannual precipitation amounts.

The resulted index values were used to determine the susceptibility classes of precipitation liable for triggering soil erosion (Table 2).

Table 2: Susceptibility classes of precipitation liable to triggering soil erosion based on Angot precipitation index (K) (Dragotă, Micu and Micu 2008; Dumitraşcu et al. 2017).

Precipitation attributes	Very dry	Dry	Normal	Rainy	Very rainy
Precipitation erodibility classes	Very low	Low	Moderate	Severe	Very severe
Angot index values (K)	< 0.99	1.00–1.49	1.50–1.99	2.00–2.49	> 2.50

In order to examine the relationship between precipitation data, K and potential climate drivers, linear correlations were utilized. The selected large-scale phenomenon, North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and Multivariate ENSO Index (MEI) were used following the approach by Malinović-Miličević et al. (2018) and Lukić et al. (2019). NAO is characterized as the difference between sea-level pressure observed over Iceland and Portugal. When the values of NAO are negative storm tracks shift to the south, inducing more winter precipitation in the regions south of the Pyrenean-Alpine Mountains, including the Pannonian Basin (and the Vojvodina Region). On the other hand, positive values of the NAO lead to shifting storm tracks to the north, exposing the area south of the Pyrenean-Alpine Mountains to relatively dry conditions in the winter (Hurrell et al. 2003; Trigo et al. 2004). The station-based NAO time series were obtained from the Climatic Research Unit of the University of East Anglia (Internet 1).

Ocean-atmosphere interactions in the Pacific realm El Niño-Southern Oscillation ($ENSO$) is one of the most important climate drivers whose influence extends across the globe. MEI is an appropriate and a rather complex parameter, which integrates complete information of six oceanic and meteorological variables indicating the influence of southern oscillation (Pompa-García and Némiga 2015). The $ENSO$ (MEI) record was obtained from the NOAA Physical Sciences Laboratory (Internet 2).

4 Results and discussion

The temporal evolution of the moving average (with a size window equal to 12 months) indicates that there are no significant variations or deviations regarding the precipitation distribution in the study area (Figure 2). This observation corresponds well with the results of Lukić et al. (2019) who pointed out that precipitation concentration values (PCI) in northern Serbia belong to the group of moderately distributed precipitation (a statistically significant trend was not observed). According to the authors, seasonal values of precipitation concentration for the Vojvodina Region generally display uniform values, where the winter season exhibits higher values than other seasons for all investigated stations during the period 1961–2014.

As shown by Bjelajac et al. (2016), the average annual precipitation (calculated for a period of 69 years) for 11 out of 12 stations indicate a positive linear trend, of which most pronounced trends are observed for the Bačka Region – Rimski Šančevi meteorological station ($y = 1.8309x + 550.89$). The highest average precipitation amount is recorded for the Bela Crkva meteorological station (659.1 mm) in the southeast, while the lowest values are recorded in the north and northeast (Palić station 555 mm and Kikinda station 555.5 mm) (Figure 3). According to the Mann-Kendall test, based on calculated p values, Sombor ($p = 0.020$) and Palić ($p = 0.021$) stations confirm the Ha hypothesis, i.e. there is a noticeable positive trend at the significance level $p < 0.05$. Therefore, on the annual basis, Sombor and Palić stations (for the study period) display an increase in the amount of precipitation by 1.46 mm and 1.68 mm, respectively (Figure 3). Other meteorological stations do not show statistically significant trend of precipitation variability for the study period.

The used meteorological database covers the warm period of the year (when positive values of K index prevail). The most favourable conditions for the occurrence of water erosion processes are distributed within April and September (when the highest rainfall amounts are recorded for all investigated stations; Figure 4). Table 3 summarizes monthly susceptibility of the Angot precipitation index classes (in%) for the selected stations during the period 1946–2014.

Figure 2: The 12-month moving average of precipitation distribution (for the study period) for the Vojvodina Region. ► p. 131

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the mean annual precipitation for the study period in the study area. ► p. 132

Figure 4: Mean monthly multiannual precipitation amounts (mm) for the selected stations and regions. ► p. 133–134

Table 3: Monthly susceptibility of Angot precipitation index classes (1946–2014).

Susceptibility class / Angot index values	Month (%)					
	April	May	June	July	August	September
Banatski Karlovac (Banat Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	56.5	52.2	20.3	53.6	59.4	62.3
Low (1.0–1.5)	31.9	17.4	26.1	13.4	18.8	20.3
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	8.7	14.5	27.5	14.5	14.5	13.1
Severe (2.1–2.5)	2.9	7.2	17.4	11.6	1.5	0
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	8.7	8.7	7.2	5.8	4.4
Bela Crkva (Banat Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	57.9	42.1	26.1	46.4	55.1	59.4
Low (1.0–1.5)	28.9	26.1	17.4	18.8	21.7	24.6
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	8.7	11.6	30.4	14.5	11.6	13.1
Severe (2.1–2.5)	4.3	10.1	10.1	8.7	7.2	0
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	10.1	15.9	11.6	4.3	2.9
Vršac (Banat Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	53.6	44.9	23.2	47.8	53.6	63.8
Low (1.0–1.5)	31.9	28.9	27.5	18.8	15.9	18.8
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	10.1	14.5	20.3	13.1	14.5	8.7
Severe (2.1–2.5)	4.3	4.3	17.4	8.7	5.8	5.8
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	7.2	11.6	11.6	10.1	2.9
Zrenjanin (Banat Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	59.4	53.6	17.4	53.6	66.6	62.3
Low (1.0–1.5)	28.9	17.4	26.1	18.8	14.5	23.2
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	10.1	15.9	27.5	10.1	10.1	8.7
Severe (2.1–2.5)	1.4	7.2	13.1	7.2	4.3	1.4
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	5.8	15.9	10.1	4.3	4.4
Kikinda (Banat Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	56.5	49.3	30.4	47.8	53.6	56.5
Low (1.0–1.5)	28.9	18.8	23.2	21.7	23.2	28.9
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	5.8	17.4	15.9	14.5	11.6	8.7
Severe (2.1–2.5)	5.8	11.6	15.9	10.1	5.8	2.9
Very severe (> 2.5)	2.9	2.9	14.5	5.8	5.8	2.9
Senta (Banat Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	69.6	46.4	24.6	59.4	50.7	57.9
Low (1.0–1.5)	18.8	21.7	27.5	20.3	27.5	24.6
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	8.7	15.9	24.6	8.7	13.1	11.6
Severe (2.1–2.5)	1.4	7.2	8.7	7.2	5.8	2.9
Very severe (> 2.5)	1.4	8.7	14.5	4.4	2.9	2.9
Bač (Bačka Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	57.9	43.5	26.1	47.8	57.9	65.2
Low (1.0–1.5)	30.4	30.4	24.6	28.9	20.3	14.5
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	10.1	13.1	24.6	14.5	11.6	8.7
Severe (2.1–2.5)	0	8.7	14.5	5.8	4.3	8.7
Very severe (> 2.5)	1.4	4.3	10.1	2.9	5.8	2.9
Bački Petrovac (Bačka Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	65.2	47.8	21.7	53.6	59.4	59.4
Low (1.0–1.5)	23.2	24.6	28.9	21.7	20.3	18.8
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	8.7	17.4	17.4	8.7	10.1	13.1
Severe (2.1–2.5)	2.9	4.3	17.4	8.7	5.8	5.8
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	5.8	14.5	7.2	4.4	2.9

Susceptibility class / Angot index values	Month (%)					
	April	May	June	July	August	September
Palić (Bačka Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	63.8	42.1	26.1	39.1	44.9	57.9
Low (1.0–1.5)	24.6	28.9	26.1	31.9	33.3	24.6
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	5.8	13.1	15.9	15.9	15.9	8.7
Severe (2.1–2.5)	4.4	10.1	20.3	8.7	1.4	4.3
Very severe (> 2.5)	1.4	5.8	11.6	4.3	4.4	4.3
Rimski Šančevi (Bačka Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	59.4	47.8	23.2	52.2	57.9	66.7
Low (1.0–1.5)	31.9	26.1	23.2	18.8	18.8	15.9
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	5.8	14.5	23.2	10.1	8.7	11.6
Severe (2.1–2.5)	1.4	7.2	14.5	11.6	10.1	4.3
Very severe (> 2.5)	1.4	4.3	15.9	7.2	4.3	1.4
Sombor (Bačka Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	56.2	49.3	26.1	40.6	59.4	65.2
Low (1.0–1.5)	33.3	23.2	24.6	21.7	23.2	18.8
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	5.8	11.6	27.5	26.1	8.7	5.8
Severe (2.1–2.5)	2.9	7.2	13.1	4.3	2.9	5.8
Very severe (> 2.5)	1.4	8.7	8.7	7.2	5.8	4.3
Sremska Mitrovica (Srem Region)						
Very low (< 1.0)	52.2	49.3	21.7	44.9	60.9	63.8
Low (1.0–1.5)	37.7	23.2	27.5	34.8	18.8	18.8
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	7.2	17.4	24.6	7.2	11.6	11.6
Severe (2.1–2.5)	2.9	4.3	15.9	7.2	4.3	2.9
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	5.8	10.1	5.8	4.3	2.9
The Autonomous Province of Vojvodina						
Very low (< 1.0)	56.5	44.9	21.7	46.4	55.1	63.8
Low (1.0–1.5)	34.8	31.9	27.5	27.5	21.7	20.3
Moderate (1.6–2.0)	7.2	10.1	27.5	14.5	14.5	11.6
Severe (2.1–2.5)	1.4	8.7	14.5	5.8	5.8	1.4
Very severe (> 2.5)	0.0	4.3	8.7	5.8	2.9	2.9

According to the *K* index values for the Banat Region, Banatski Karlovac meteorological station records, the presence of very severe rainfall erosivity occurred in 1975 and 2014. On the other hand, the presence of moderate erosion classes is evenly distributed during the two thirty-year cycles in the study period. Bela Crkva station follows a similar pattern. After 1975, an increase of very severe precipitation classes has been observed during the studied six-month interval. The most pronounced very severe precipitation erosion classes have been observed for the Vršac station in 1995. During the study period, this station does not record the presence of severe erosion classes except in 2014 (during May, August and September). This observation corresponds with the results of Lukić et al. (2019), who pointed out that the weather station Vršac (*MFI* – 149.16) and its surroundings have the highest erosivity value for 2014. The Zrenjanin station records very severe rainfall erosivity classes in 2010 and 2014. The number of precipitation months classified as severe and very severe erosion have been increasing since 1999 (Figure 5). The weather station Kikinda does not display extreme rainfall erosivity, during the investigated period. 2001 is highlighted as a year where severe erosion occurred in April, June and September. Extreme precipitation sums (registered in 2014) for the weather station of Senta indicate the presence of very severe erosion during May, July and September. Years with the distinguished presence of very severe erosion classes (33.3% of the studied precipitation interval) are 1974, 1978, 1999, 2001 and 2004. This implies that the area surrounding Senta weather station is somewhat more prone to rainfall erosivity.

Figure 5: Mean multiannual values of *K* Index during the warm part of the year for Banat weather stations. ► p. 137–139

Banatski Karlovac

Bela Crkva

Kikinda

Senta

According to the K index values for the Bačka Region, the Bač weather station in the western part of Vojvodina Region, registers several years with the two-month precipitation interval presence of very severe erosion classes (2001, 2005 and 2014). The presence of low values of the K index corresponds well with the observations provided by Bjelajac et al. (2016). The Bački Petrovac station does not display a higher presence of severe erosion classes during the study period. The years with the presence of severe erosion classes within the 33.3% of the precipitation interval are 1975, 2005 and 2014. On the other hand, the Palić weather station in the north of the Vojvodina province generally displays an absence of periods with intensive rainfall erosivity classes. These observations fit well with the finding of Lukić et al. (2019), that Palić area records the lowest erosivity value in the Vojvodina Region during 1983 ($MFI = 8.60$). Results for the Rimski Šančevi weather station in the southern parts of Bačka Region indicate that an increase of rainfall erosivity can be seen from 1995, with the presence of three-month precipitation intervals of very severe erosion in 2001. Lukić et al. (2019) indicate that this part of the Pannonian Basin is characterized by periods of irregular precipitation concentration and an increase of MFI values on an annual basis. These features suggest a rather wetter conditions in this part of Vojvodina Region. The Sombor weather station generally registers weaker rainfall erosivity, with an exception of extreme rainy years (Figure 6).

According to the K index values for the Srem Region, the Sremska Mitrovica weather station does not identify higher three-month precipitation intervals of severe and very severe erosion classes. The years 1972, 2001 and 2014 record two-month precipitation intervals of very severe erosion. Three-month precipitation intervals of very severe erosion classes were only present during the extremely rainy 2014. The years of 1975 and 2001 record two-month precipitation intervals of the highest erosion classes. During the period 1946–2014, the highest presence of very low and low rainfall erosivity classes can be observed (Figure 7).

Similar approach related to the hydro-meteorological hazard assessment has been performed by Dumitraşcu et al. (2017) for the south-western part of Romania. Previously, Dragotă et al. (2014) pointed out that the Danube Floodplain displays moderate to excessive rainfall erosivity regime. Authors emphasize that due to relief configuration, reduced declivity and soil types, moderate, low and very low susceptibility classes prevail in the study area. On the other hand, Dumitraşcu et al. (2017) showed that mountainous and hilly areas display the highest susceptibility to rainfall erosivity, as it can be observed for south-eastern parts of the Vojvodina Region (Banat Region with Vršac weather station) (Figure 8). As the altitude drops, severe and very severe class values are approximately equally distributed on a multiannual basis corresponding to the findings in a neighbouring country. As observed for the Romanian plain and the Danube valley, very low and low classes dominate, especially in April, August and September, which is in accordance with the obtained mean K values for the Vojvodina Region (Figure 8). On the other hand, Lukić et al. (2019) suggest that both the amount and the intensity of precipitation are increasing and varying in some areas of the Pannonian Basin. The trends generally indicate a progressive increase in the values of the erosion by precipitation at the annual level, which in future may lead to the transition to a higher erosive class and increase the vulnerability to this type of erosion in the Pannonian Basin and Vojvodina Region. Also, the relief properties and the interaction with the general atmospheric circulation in the study area greatly contribute to the spatial pattern of rainfall erodibility potential in terms of intensity, frequency and spatial distribution (Figures 3 and 8). These spatial features correspond with the *RUSLE* soil loss results, presented by Borrelli et al. (2017).

In agricultural areas, evaluation of the vulnerability associated with the high impact of rainfall erosivity is of utmost importance in the context of sustainable agricultural practices and specific local or regional climate conditions (Komac and Zorn 2005; Maracchi, Sirotenko and Bindi 2005). Accordingly, a good understanding of climate variability and main precipitation features is of great importance, especially when dealing with rainfall erosivity in agricultural areas such as Vojvodina Region.

Figure 6: Mean multiannual values of K Index during the warm part of the year for Bačka weather stations. ► p. 141–143

Figure 7: Mean multiannual values of K Index during the warm part of the year for Srem weather station and the Vojvodina Region. ► p. 144

Figure 8: Distribution of the mean K Index classes for the observed period and comparison with the *RUSLE* soil loss values (adapted after Borrelli et al. 2017). ► p. 145

Bač

Bački Petrovac

Sremska Mitrovica

The Autonomous Province of Vojvodina

In order to protect areas that are potentially endangered by rainfall erosion, it is necessary to assess the intensity of these processes, and then evaluate the negative impact of social structures. As pointed out by Panagos et al. (2015a), rainfall erosivity in Europe is a key parameter for estimating soil erosion loss and risk in various regions. Authors outline that the European continental climatic zone is characterized by warm summers and cold winters, and thus highly susceptible to the variability of rainfall erosivity. The mean rainfall erosivity factor for the Pannonian zone (central Danubian basin) is $660.1 \text{ MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and corresponds well with the findings of Mezősi and Bata (2016) and Lukić et al. (2019).

The results of *NAO* and *MEI* indices were correlated with the mean annual precipitation data for the study area and *K* index values. Correlation between the teleconnection patterns and precipitation parameters was estimated in order to investigate the possible relationships between rainfall erosivity and atmospheric variability by applying Pearson's correlation analysis at the 5% ($p < 0.05$) significance level. A correlation between the *NAO* index and precipitation (-0.19), as well as the *K* index (-0.20), is presented in Figure 9. The negative correlation coefficient indicates the wetting effect on the *K* index. Based on contemporary findings it can be pointed out that *NAO* considerably affects rainfall in this part of Europe (e.g., Tošić et al. 2014; Luković et al. 2015; Radaković et al. 2018), and since the *K* index is based on precipitation amounts, *NAO* has a certain influence on it as well. As pointed out by Bice et al. (2012), *NAO* generally has a strong influence on winter precipitation in the Pannonian Basin, with negative *NAO* phases corresponding to periods of high precipitation. Results of Malinović-Milićević et al. (2018) indicate that the amount and intensity of precipitation in Serbia had a statistically significant increase during autumn, and were most pronounced in the northern (Vojvodina) and western parts of the country. The authors showed that »dry« regimes dominate over »wet«, with an increasing trend of »warm« regimes and decreasing trend of »cold« regimes. The correlation between the examined extreme indices and the large-scale circulation patterns showed that East Atlantic (*EA*) and *NAO* patterns had a significant influence on the duration of winter warm periods, while their influence on the duration of cold periods cannot be confirmed with certainty. The East Atlantic/West Russia (*EAWR*) pattern affects statistically significant positive autumn trends of all intensity and frequency indices. In winter, it has an impact on the frequency of »dry« and »wet« conditions and the intensity of the precipitation. On the other hand, the correlation between *MEI* and precipitation (0.006) cannot be confirmed for the given significance level ($p < 0.05$). Hence, no significant correlations were detected between observed precipitation parameters, *NAO* and *MEI*, thus generally indicating the absence of strong linearity between the *K*, and these two large-scale processes of climate variability. As shown by Dehghani et al. (2020), large-scale circulation drivers have a considerable impact on precipitation in different regions, where various climate indices in different phases may decrease the seasonal precipitation (even up to 100%). On the other hand, seasonal precipitation may increase more than 100% in different seasons due to the impact of these indices.

5 Conclusion

Soil erosion by water has often been overlooked (Zorn 2015) as an important land degradation (Zorn and Komac 2013b) and environmental problem. In the Soil Thematic Strategy of the European Commission (Communication ... 2006) it is listed among the eight main threats to soil in the EU (Panagos 2015b).

In this study the *K* index was used to determinate the characteristic types of monthly and annual variation of precipitation based on regional and local comparisons. Results of this study indicate that the Vojvodina Region has experienced the presence of various susceptibility classes of precipitation liable for triggering soil erosion from April until September. June and July are the months with higher frequency of very severe erodibility classes, with the distribution of 8.70% and 5.80%, respectively. Most of the distributed erodibility classes observed for the study area belong to moderate, varying from 7.25% (in April) up to 27.54% (in June). On the other hand, a progressive increase in the values of the rainfall erosivity at the annual level (induced by climate variability), in the future can lead to the transition to a higher erosive class and increase the vulnerability to rainfall erosion in the Pannonian continental climatic zone.

Figure 9: Correlation between *NAO* and precipitation (a), *NAO* and *K* Index (b), and *MEI* and precipitation (c). ► p. 147

As precipitation is seen as one of the main triggering factors for flash floods, landslides, and soil erosion, future extreme weather events are likely to have seriously damaging effects on crops and pastures, thus changing the land use and land cover.

In the further research it is necessary to look more into the relationship between *NAO* and its impact on changes in seasonal precipitation. For Serbia, these changes should be investigated in detail using a wet season concept between October and March, as previously discussed by Luković et al. (2015). This approach may be suitable since it could investigate the probability of an increase or decrease in precipitation amounts associated with the above-mentioned indices and seasonal rainfall erosivity rates as well.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: The authors acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-68/2020-14/ 200125). A part of the research was supported by the H2020 WIDESPREAD-05-2020 – Twinning: ExtremeClimTwin that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952384, and the Slovenian Research Agency research programme Geography of Slovenia (grant No. P6-0101). We confirm that all the authors made an equal contribution to the study and its development. Authors are grateful to the anonymous reviewer's whose comments and suggestions greatly improved the manuscript.

6 References

- Alexandersson, H. 1986: A homogeneity test applied to precipitation data. *Journal of Climatology* 6-6. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.3370060607>
- Alipour, Z. T., Mahdian, M. H., Pazira, E., Hakimkhani, S., Saeedi, M. 2012: The determination of the best rainfall erosivity index for Namak lake basin and evaluation of Spatial Variations. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research* 2-1.
- Angulo-Martínez, M., Beguería, S. 2009: Estimating rainfall erosivity from daily precipitation records: A comparison among methods using data from the Ebro Basin (NE Spain). *Journal of Hydrology* 379-1,2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2009.09.051>
- Apaydin, H., Erpul, G., Bayramin, I., Gabriels, D. 2006: Evaluation of indices for characterizing the distribution and concentration of precipitation: A case for the region of Southeastern Anatolia Project, Turkey. *Journal of Hydrology* 328-3,4. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2006.01.019>
- Arnoldus, H. M. J. 1980: An approximation of the rainfall factor in the Universal Soil Loss Equation. *Assessment of Erosion*. Chichester.
- Auerswald, K., Fiener, P., Martin, W., Elhaus, D. 2014: Use and misuse of the K factor equation in soil erosion modeling: An alternative equation for determining USLE nomograph soil erodibility values. *Catena* 118. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2014.01.008>
- Basarin, B., Lukić, T., Mesaroš, M., Pavić, D., Đorđević, J., Matzarakis, A. 2018: Spatial and temporal analysis of extreme bioclimate conditions in Vojvodina, Northern Serbia. *International Journal of Climatology* 38-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5166>
- Bayramin, I., Erpul, G., Erdogan, H. E. 2006: Use of CORINE methodology to assess soil erosion risk in the semi-arid area of Beypazari, Ankara. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry* 30.
- Bice, D., Montanari, A., Vučetić, V., Vučetić, M. 2012: The influence of regional and global climatic oscillations on Croatian climate. *International Journal of Climatology* 32-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.2372>
- Bjelajac, D., Lukić, T., Micić, T., Miljković, Đ., Sakulski, D. 2016: Rainfall erosivity as an indicator of potential threat to erosion vulnerability in protected areas of Vojvodina (North Serbia). *Proceedings of the International Conference on Monitoring and Management of Visitors in Recreational and Protected Areas*. Novi Sad.
- Blinkov, I. 2015a: The Balkans – The most erosive part of Europe? *Bulletin of the Faculty of Forestry* 111. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2298/GSF1511009B>
- Blinkov, I. 2015b: Review and comparison of water erosion intensity in the Western Balkan and EU countries. *Contributions Section of Natural, Mathematical and Biotechnical Sciences* 36-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20903/csnmb.masa.2015.36.1.63>

- Boardman, J., Poesen, J. (eds.) 2006: Soil erosion in Europe. Chichester. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/0470859202>
- Boardman, J., Vandaele, K., Evans, R., Foster I. D. L. 2019: Off-site impacts of soil erosion and runoff: Why connectivity is more important than erosion rates. *Soil Use Management* 35-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12496>
- Borrelli, P., Alewell, C., Alvarez, P., Ayach Anache, J. A., Baartman, J., Ballabio, C., Bezak, N., Biddoccu, M., Cerdà, A., Chalise, D., Chen, S., Chen, W., de Girolamo, A. M., Gessesse, G. D., Deumlich, D., Diodato, N., Efthimiou, N., Erpul, G., Fiener, P., Freppaz, M., Gentile, F., Gericke, A., Haregeweyn, N., Hu, B., Jeanneau, A., Kaffas, K., Kiani-Harchegani, M., Lizaga Villuendas, I., Li, C., Lombardo, L., López-Vicente, M., Lucas-Borja, M. E., Märker, M., Matthew, F., Miao, C., Mikoš, M., Modugno, S., Möller, M., Naipal, V., Nearing, M., Owusu, S., Panday, D., Patault, E., Patriche, C. V., Poggio, L., Portes, R., Quijano, L., Rahdari, M. R., Renima, M., Ricci, G. F., Rodrigo-Comino, J., Saia, S., Samani, A. N., Schillaci, C., Syrris, V., Kim, H. S., Spinola, D. N., Oliveira, P. T., Teng, H., Thapa, R., Vantas, K., Vieira, D., Yang, J. E., Yin, S., Zema, D. M., Zhao, G., Panagos, P. 2021: Soil erosion modelling: A global review and statistical analysis. *Science of The Total Environment* 780. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146494>
- Borrelli, P., Robinson, D. A., Fleischer, L. R., Lugato, E., Ballabio, C., Alewell, C., Meusburger, K., Modugno, S., Schütt, B., Ferro, V., Bagarello, V., Van Oost, K., Montanarella, L., Panagos, P. 2017: An assessment of the global impact of 21st century land use change on soil erosion. *Nature Communications* 8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02142-7>
- Bosco, C., de Rigo, D., Dewitte, O., Poesen, J., Panagos, P. 2015: Modelling soil erosion at European scale: Towards harmonization and reproducibility. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 15-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-15-225-2015>
- Cohen, J. 1988. *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. New York.
- Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection. Commission of the European communities. Internet: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52006DC0231&from=EN> (14. 9. 2021)
- Constantin, D. M., Vătămanu, V. V. 2015: Considerations upon the dryness and drought phenomena in the Caracal plain, Romania. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development* 15-1.
- Costea, M. 2012: Using the Fournier Indexes in estimating rainfall erosivity. Case study – The Secașul Mare Basin. *Air and Water Components of the Environment Conference*. Cluj-Napoca.
- da Silva, A. M. 2004: Rainfall erosivity map for Brazil. *Catena* 57-3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2003.11.006>
- De Luis, M., González-Hidalgo, J. C., Bruneti, M., Longares, L. A. 2011: Precipitation concentration changes in Spain 1946–2005. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-11-1259-2011>
- De Luis, M., González-Hidalgo, J. C., Longares, L. A. 2010: Is rainfall erosivity increasing in the Mediterranean Iberian Peninsula? *Land Degradation and Development* 21-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.918>
- Dehghani, M., Salehi, S., Mosavi, A., Nabipour, N., Shamshirband, S., Ghamisi, P. 2020: Spatial analysis of seasonal precipitation over Iran: Co-variation with climate indices. *International Journal of Geo-Information* 9-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9020073>
- Diodato, N., Bellocchi, G. 2007: Estimating monthly (*R*) USLE climate input in a Mediterranean region using limited data. *Journal of Hydrology* 345-3,4. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2007.08.008>
- Dragotă, C. S., Grigorescu, I., Dumitrașcu, M., Kucsicsa, G. 2014: Pluvial hazards assessment in the Danube floodplain. The Calafat–Turnu Măgurele sector. *Problems of Geography* 1-2.
- Dragotă, C. S., Micu, M., Micu, D. 2008: The relevance of pluvial regime for landslides genesis and evolution. Case study: Muscel basin (Buzău Subcarpathians), Romania. *Present Environment and Sustainable Development* 2.
- Dumitrașcu, M., Dragotă, C. S., Grigorescu, I., Dumitrașcu, C., Vlăduț, A. 2017: Key pluvial parameters in assessing rainfall erosivity in the south-west development region, Romania. *Journal of Earth System Science* 126. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12040-017-0834-y>

- Ferk, M., Ciglić, R., Komac, B., Lóczy, D. 2020: Management of small retention ponds and their impact on flood hazard prevention in the Slovenske Gorice Hills. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 60-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS.7675>
- Fournier, F. 1960: *Climat et erosion, la relation entre l'érosion du sol par l'eau et les précipitations atmosphériques*. Paris.
- Gabriels, D. 2001: Rain erosivity in Europe. Man and soil in the third millennium. Logrono.
- Gavrilov, M. B., Lazić, L., Milutinović, M., Gavrilov, M. M. 2011: Influence of hail suppression on the hail trend in Vojvodina, Serbia. *Geographica Pannonica* 15-2.
- Gavrilov, M. B., Marković, S. B., Jarad, A., Korać, V. M. 2015: The analysis of temperature trends in Vojvodina (Serbia) from 1949 to 2006. *Thermal Science* 19-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2298/TSCI150207062G>
- Gavrilov, M. B., Marković, S. B., Zorn, M., Komac, B., Lukić, T., Milošević, M., Janičević, S. 2013: Is hail suppression useful in Serbia? General review and new results. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 53-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS53302>
- Gavrilov, M. B., Radaković, M. G., Sipos, G., Mezősi, G., Gavrilov, G., Lukić, T., Basarin, B., Benyhe, B., Fiala, K., Kozák, P., Perić, Z. M., Govedarica, D., Song, Y., Marković, S. B. 2020: Aridity in the Central and Southern Pannonian Basin. *Atmosphere* 11-12. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11121269>
- Gavrilov, M. B., Tošić, I., Marković, S. B., Unkašević, M., Petrović, P. 2016: Analysis of annual and seasonal temperature trends using the Mann-Kendall test in Vojvodina, Serbia. *Időjárás* 120-2.
- Gavrilov, M. B., Lukić, T., Janc, N., Basarin, B., Marković, S. B. 2019: Forestry Aridity Index in Vojvodina, North Serbia. *Open Geosciences* 11-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/geo-2019-0029>
- Gavrilović, S. 1972: *Inženjering o bujičnim tokovima i eroziji*. Beograd.
- Gilbert, R. O. 1987: *Statistical methods for environmental pollution monitoring*. New York.
- Gocić, M., Trajković, S. 2013: Analysis of precipitation and drought data in Serbia over the period 1980–2010. *Journal of Hydrology* 494. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2013.04.044>
- Hernando, D., Romana, M. G. 2015: Estimating the rainfall erosivity factor from monthly precipitation data in the Madrid Region (Spain). *Journal of Hydrology and Hydromechanics* 63-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/johh-2015-0003>
- Hrnjak, I., Lukić, T., Gavrilov, M. B., Marković, S. B., Unkašević, M., Tošić, I. 2014: Aridity in Vojvodina, Serbia. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 115. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-013-0893-1>
- Hrvatina, M., Ciglić, R., Lóczy, D., Zorn, M. 2019: Določanje erozije v gričevjih severovzhodne Slovenije z Gavrilovićevo enačbo. *Geografski vestnik* 91-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/GV91206>
- Hudson, N. W. 1976: *Soil conservation*. London.
- Hurrell, J. W., Kushnir, Y., Visbeck, M., Ottersen, G. 2003. *An Overview of the North Atlantic Oscillation. Climatic Significance and Environmental Impact*. Washington D. C.
- Internet 1: <https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/cru/data/nao/> (7. 4. 2020).
- Internet 2: <https://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/ENSO/MEI/table.html> (7. 4. 2020).
- Iskander, S. M., Rajib, M. A., Rahman, M. M. 2014: Trending regional precipitation distribution and intensity: Use of climatic indices. *Atmospheric and Climate Sciences* 4-3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4236/acs.2014.43038>
- Kendall, M. 1938: A new measure of rank correlation. *Biometrika* 30.
- Kendall, M. G. 1975: *Rank correlation methods*. London.
- Kirkby, M. J., Neale, R. H. 1987: *A soil erosion model incorporating seasonal factors*. Chichester.
- Komac, B., Zorn, M. 2005: Soil erosion on agricultural land in Slovenia – Measurements of rill erosion in the Besnica valley. *Acta geographica Slovenica* DOI: 45-1. <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS45103>
- Lal, R. 1976: Soil erosion on Alfisols in Western Nigeria: III. Effects of rainfall characteristics. *Geoderma* 16-5. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7061\(76\)90003-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7061(76)90003-3)
- Leger, M. 1990: Loess landforms. *Quaternary International* 7-8. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/1040-6182\(90\)90038-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/1040-6182(90)90038-6)
- Loureiro, N. D., Coutinho, M. D. 2001: A new procedure to estimate the RUSLE EI30 index, based on monthly rainfall data and applied to the Algarve region, Portugal. *Journal of Hydrology* 250-1,4. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(01\)00387-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(01)00387-0)
- Lujan, D. L., Gabriels, D. 2005: Assessing the rain erosivity and rain distribution in different agro-climatic zones in Venezuela. *Sociedade and Natureza* 1-1.

- Lukić, T., Bjelajac, D., Fitzsimmons, K. E., Marković, S. B., Basarin, B., Mladan, D., Micić, T., Schaetzl, J. R., Gavrilov, M. B., Milanović, M., Sipos, G., Mezósi, G., Knežević Lukić, N., Milinčić, M., Létal, A., Samardžić, I. 2018: Factors triggering landslide occurrence on the Zemun loess plateau, Belgrade area, Serbia. *Environmental Earth Sciences* 77. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-018-7712-z>
- Lukić, T., Gavrilov, M. B., Marković, S. B., Komac, B., Zorn, M., Mladan, D., Đorđević, J., Milanović, M., Vasiljević, Dj. A., Vujičić, M. D., Kuzmanović, B., Prentović, R. 2013: Classification of natural disasters between the legislation and application: Experience of the Republic of Serbia. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 53-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS53301>
- Lukić, T., Leščičen, I., Sakulski, D., Basarin, B., Jordaan, A. 2016: Rainfall erosivity as an indicator of sliding occurrence along the southern slopes of the Bačka loess plateau: A case study of the Kula settlement, Vojvodina (North Serbia). *Carpathian Journal of Earth and Environmental Sciences* 11-2.
- Lukić, T., Lukić, A., Basarin, B., Micić Ponjiger, T., Blagojević, D., Mesaroš, M., Milanović, M., Gavrilov, M. B., Pavić, D., Zorn, M., Komac, B., Miljković, Đ., Sakulski, D., Babić-Kekez, S., Morar, C., Janičević, S. 2019: Rainfall erosivity and extreme precipitation in the Pannonian basin. *Open Geosciences* 11-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/geo-2019-0053>
- Lukić, T., Marić, P., Hrnjak, I., Gavrilov, M. B., Mladjan, D., Zorn, M., Komac, B., Milošević, Z., Marković, S. B., Sakulski, D., Jordaan, A., Đorđević, J., Pavić, D., Stojavljević, R. 2017: Forest fire analysis and classification based on a Serbian case study. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 57-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS.918>
- Lukić, T., Marković, S. B., Stevens, T., Vasiljević, Dj. A., Machalett, B., Milojković, N., Basarin, B., Obreht, I. 2009: The loess cave near the village of Surduk – an unusual pseudokarst landform in the loess of Vojvodina, Serbia. *Acta Carsologica* 38-2,3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/ac.v38i2-3.124>
- Luković, J., Blagojević, D., Kilibarda, M., Bajat, B. 2015: Spatial pattern of North Atlantic Oscillation impact on rainfall in Serbia. *Spatial Statistics* 14-A. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spasta.2015.04.007>
- Lung, T., Hilden, M. 2017: Multi-sectoral vulnerability and risks: Socioeconomic scenarios for Europe. *Climate Change, Impacts and Vulnerability in Europe 2016. An indicator-based report*. Luxembourg.
- Malinović-Miličević, S., Mihailović, D. T., Radovanović, M. M., Drešković, N. 2018. Extreme precipitation indices in Vojvodina Region (Serbia). *Journal of the Geographical Institute Jovan Cvijić SASA* 68-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2298/IJGI1801001M>
- Maracchi, G., Sirotenko, O., Bindi, M. 2005: Impacts of present and future climate variability on agriculture and forestry in the temperate regions: Europe. *Increasing Climate Variability and Change*. Dordrecht. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-4166-7_6
- Marković, S. B., Bokhorst, M., Vandenberghe, J., Oches, E. A., Zöller, L., McCoy, W. D., Gaudenyi, T., Jovanović, M., Hambach, U., Machalett, B. 2008: Late Pleistocene loess-palaeosol sequences in the Vojvodina region, north Serbia. *Journal of Quaternary Science* 23-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.1124>
- Marković, S. B., Hambach, U., Stevens, T., Jovanović, M., O'Hara-Dhand, K., Basarin, B., Lu, H., Smalley, I., Buggle, B., Zech, M., Svirčev, Z., Sümegei, P., Milojković, N., Zöller, L. 2012: Loess in the Vojvodina region (Northern Serbia): An essential link between European and Asian Pleistocene environments. *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences* 91-1,2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016774600001578>
- Marković, S. B., Stevens, T., Kukla, G. J., Hambach, U., Fitzsimmons, K. E., Gibbard, P., Buggle, B., Zech, M., Guo, Z., Hao, Q., Wu, H., O'Hara Dhand, K., Smalley, I. J., Újvári, G., Sümegei, P., Timar-Gabor, A., Veres, D., Sirocko, F., Vasiljević, Dj. A., Jary, Z., Svensson, A., Jović, V., Lehmkuhl, F., Kovács, J., Svirčev, Z. 2015: Danube loess stratigraphy – Towards a pan-European loess stratigraphic model. *Earth-Science Reviews* 148. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2015.06.005>
- Martínez-Casasnovas, J. A., Ramos, M. C., Ribes-Dasi, M. 2002: Soil erosion caused by extreme rainfall events: Mapping and quantification in agricultural plots from very detailed digital elevation models. *Geoderma* 105-1,2. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(01\)00096-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(01)00096-9)
- Mello, C. R., Viola, M. R., Beskow, S., Norton, L. D. 2013: Multivariate models for annual rainfall erosivity in Brazil. *Geoderma* 202, 203. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2013.03.009>
- Meteorološki godišnjak 1946–2014. Republički hidrometeorološki zavod. Beograd. Internet: http://www.hidmet.gov.rs/latin/meteorologija/klimatologija_godisnjaci.php (12. 5. 2021).
- Mezősi, G., Bata, T. 2016: Estimation of the changes in the rainfall erosivity in Hungary. *Journal of Environmental Geography* 9-3,4. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/jengeo-2016-0011>

- Milanović, M. M, Micić, T., Lukić, T., Nenadović, S. S., Basarin, B., Filipović, D., Tomić, M., Samardžić, I., Srdić, Z., Nikolić, G., Ninković, M. M., Sakulski, D., Ristanović, B. 2019: Application of Landsat-derived NDVI in monitoring and assessment of vegetation cover changes in Central Serbia. *Carpathian Journal of Earth and Environmental Sciences* 14-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26471/cjees/2019/014/064>
- Morgan, R. P. C. 2005: Soil erosion and conservation. Oxford.
- Nearing, M. A., Yin, S-q., Borrelli, P., Polyakov, V. O. 2017: Rainfall erosivity: An historical review. *Catena* 157. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2017.06.004>
- Oduro-Afriyie, K. 1996: Rainfall erosivity map for Ghana. *Geoderma* 74-1,2. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(96\)00054-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(96)00054-7)
- Onchev, N. G. 1985: Universal index for calculating rainfall erosivity. *Soil Erosion and Conservation*. Ankeny.
- Panagos, P., Ballabio, C., Borrelli, P., Meusburger, K., Klik, A., Rousseva, S., Perčec Tadić, M., Michaelides, S., Hrabalíková, M., Olsen, P., Aalto, J., Lakatos, M., Rymaszewicz, A., Dumitrescu, A., Beguería, S., Alewell, C. 2015a: Rainfall erosivity in Europe. *Science of The Total Environment* 511. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.01.008>
- Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Meusburger, K., Yu, B., Klik, A., Lim, K. J., Yang, J. E, Ni, J., Miao, C., Chattopadhyay, N., Sadeghi, S. H., Hazbavi, Z., Zabihi, M., Larionov, G. A., Krasnov, S. F., Garobets, A., Levi, Y., Erpul, G., Birkel, C., Hoyos, N., Naipal, V., Oliveira, P. T. S., Bonilla, C. A., Meddi, M., Nel, W., Dashti, H., Boni, M., Diodato, N., Van Oost, K., Nearing, M. A., Ballabio, C. 2017: Global rainfall erosivity assessment based on high-temporal resolution rainfall records. *Scientific Reports* 7. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-04282-8>
- Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Poesen, J., Ballabio, C., Lugato, E., Meusburger, K., Montanarella, L., Alewell, C. 2015b: The new assessment of soil loss by water erosion in Europe. *Environmental Science and Policy* 54. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.08.012>
- Pompa-García, M., Némiga, X. A. 2015: ENSO index teleconnection with seasonal precipitation in a temperate ecosystem of northern Mexico. *Atmósfera* 28-1. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0187-6236\(15\)72158-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0187-6236(15)72158-2)
- Radaković, M. G., Tošić, I., Bačević, N., Mladjan, D., Gavrilov, M. B., Marković, S. B. 2018: The analysis of aridity in Central Serbia from 1949 to 2015. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 133. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-017-2220-8>
- Renard, K. G., Foster, G. R., Weesies, G. A., McCool, D. K., Yoder, D. C. 1997: Predicting soil erosion by water: A guide to conservation planning with the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE). Washington D.C.
- Renard, K.G, Freimund, J.R. 1994: Using monthly precipitation data to estimate the *R*-factor in the revised USLE. *Journal of Hydrology* 157-1,2,3,4. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694\(94\)90110-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694(94)90110-4)
- Sanchez-Moreno, J. F., Mannaerts, C. M., Jetten, V. 2014: Rainfall erosivity mapping for Santiago Island, Cape Verde. *Geoderma* 217,218. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2013.10.026>
- Santos Telles, T., de Fátima Guimarães, M., Falci Dechen, S. C. 2011: The costs of soil erosion. *Revista Brasileira de Ciência do Solo* 35-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-06832011000200001>
- Šmid Hribar, M., Geršič, M., Pipan, P., Repolusk, P., Tiran, J., Topole, M., Ciglič, R. 2017: Cultivated terraces in Slovenian landscapes. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 57-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS.4597>
- Stroosnijder, L. 2005: Measurement of erosion: Is it possible? *Catena* 64-2,3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2005.08.004>
- Tošić, I., Hrnjak, I., Gavrilov, M. B., Unkašević, M., Marković, S. B., Lukić, T. 2014: Annual and seasonal variability of precipitation in Vojvodina, Serbia. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 117. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-013-1007-9>
- Trigo, M. R., Pozo-Vazquez, D., Osborn, J. T., Castro-Diez, Y., Gamiz-Fortis, S., Esteban-Parra, J. M. 2004: North Atlantic oscillation influence on precipitation, river flow and water resources in the Iberian Peninsula. *International Journal of Climatology* 24-8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1048>
- Ufoegbune, G. C., Bello, N. J., Ojekunle, Z. O., Orunkoye, A. R., Eruola, A. O., Amori, A. A. 2011: Rainfall erosivity pattern of Ogun River basin area (Nigeria) using Modified Fournier Index. *European Water* 35.
- Vasiljević, Dj. A., Marković, S. B., Hose, T. A., Smalley, I., O'Hara Dhand, K., Basarin, B., Lukić, T., Vujičić, M. D. 2011: Loess towards (geo) tourism – Proposed application on loess in Vojvodina region (North Serbia). *Acta geographica Slovenica* 51-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3986/AGS51305>
- Wischmeier, W. H., Smith, D. D. 1978: Predicting rainfall erosion losses: A guide to conservation planning. Washington D. C.

- Yu, B. 1998: Rainfall erosivity and its estimation for Australia's tropics. *Australian Journal of Soil Research* 36-1.
- Yu, B., Neil, D. T. 2000: Empirical catchment-wide rainfall erosivity models for two rivers in the humid tropics of Australia. *Australian Geographer* 31-1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049180093565>
- Yue, B. J., Shi, Z. H., Fang, N. F. 2014: Evaluation of rainfall erosivity and its temporal variation in the Yanhe River catchment of the Chinese Loess Plateau. *Natural Hazards* 74. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-014-1199-z>
- Yue, S., Pilon, P., Phinney, B., Cavadias, G. 2002: The influence of autocorrelation on the ability to detect trend in hydrological series. *Hydrological Processes* 16-9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.1095>
- Zorn, M. 2015: Erozija prsti – prežrt okoljski problem. *Geografski obzornik* 63-2,3.
- Zorn, M., Komac, B. 2013a: Erosion. *Encyclopedia of Natural Hazards*. Dordrecht. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4399-4_120
- Zorn, M., Komac, B. 2013b: Land degradation. *Encyclopedia of Natural Hazards*. Dordrecht. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4399-4_207